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THE CHANGING INDIAN RETAILING SCENE

Dr. Padma Yallapragada

Senior Business instructor,
National Institute for Vocational Education (NIVE),
Knowledge and Human Development Authority (KHDA),
Government of Dubai, Dubai – United Arab Emirates (UAE)

Abstract

The Retail industry is changing drastically and rapidly with leaps and bounds. To accommodate this change, there is a shift from consumer end and also from retailer's end. This paper highlights the applicability of the change esp. for individual consumer and also brings the differentiation in a methodical manner. This paper also studies the problem at the customer level and illustrates the suggestions to retail outlets by setting up hypotheses. As the problem of this study is of very recent origin in the Indian context, not many studies seem to have been done with any sound research method and I have examined only one type of retail outlets, i.e. Kirana or general stores or mom and pop stores as they are commonly known. Many more reasons can be defined for the spurt in this retail activity, but the question arises where will all this lead the economy and the country to? What are the repercussions and outcome of all this? What will happen to the several million of small and medium retail outlets functioning throughout the country, who are seeking their livelihood in the country?

The theme of this paper is to study the above hypothesis and conclude that that the opening of supermarkets in India is not likely to affect the lives of several millions of small and independent retailers in a big way. This paper also projects the future research topic as a seamless extension to the current title with regards to the longevity of these Kirana stores and co-existence along with supermarkets.

Keywords: Retail, Supermarkets, Consumers, Kirana, Economy

Introduction

The Indian retailing scene is drastically undergoing a change. Particularly in the urban areas the change is spectacular with many corporate houses entering retail business. These changes are too markedly visible in the post-liberalization era. While retail chains such as Bata, Carona, Wheelers, Spencer's of Mark Spencer's are not uncommon in India. Big corporate bodies and multi-nationals entering retailing business is relatively recent phenomenon. Cloth retailing is another business which grew big in the size of the shops as also many retail chains have emerged in early 90's. Big bazaars, Sunterra, Apna Bazaar, Ratnadeep and other so-called super-markets began emerging in different parts of urban areas. Attracted by the changes that are coming forth in the urban retailing scenario of the country and also being encouraged by the liberalization policies pursued by successive union governments, the international retail giants such as Tesco are planning to enter the country with their super-market chains as joint ventures.

REASONS FOR THE SPURT IN BIG RETAIL STORE ACTIVITIES

The reasons for the spurt in big retail stores activity are as follows:

1. Owing to excessive urbanization, population in the cities and big towns is growing by leaps and bounds, making them attractive markets for those who have the financial clout to start big stores.
2. Retailing business is seen as less risky with reasonably good and safe margins.
3. Slack governmental control and regulation of business is making the business man consider retailing as a safe haven.
4. Some of these corporate houses are also manufacturers and marketers of several consumer goods. Starting of big retail outlets are likely to benefit them in more ways than one.
 - Their brands get greater exposure which can reduce their advertising budgets.
 - They can grow closely in a highly competitive world, so much so that they can have their finger on the pulse of the consumer directly.
 - They can retain the margins which they were allowing the wholesalers and retailers earlier to themselves.
 - Part of these profits can be given back to the consumer in the form of lower prices or discounts, thereby attracting consumers to their shops in larger numbers and which may lead switching from street corner retail outlets and hawkers to the super-markets and hyper markets.
5. As real estates and lands in the urban areas are becoming dearer, mall culture is increasingly becoming popular and large turnout at these malls is making it attractive for companies to go in for departmental stores and super-markets.
6. To a certain extent, the concept of fluctuating demand in industrial markets is also making the big houses to enter this business in a big way. One of the properties of industrial demand is: if one business house becomes successful in a line of business, other business men swarm that business and hundreds join the band wagon. If one or two units fail in succession all the business units leave the business and go in for greener pastures. It is safe to hypothesize in the present context also, that corporate houses are vying to join retail business and become the members of the prestigious club as soon as possible. Tata's have already entered, Birla's, Godrej and Reliance already joined. Mahindra's are ready to jump into it now.

Many more reasons can be defined for the spurt in this retail activity, but where will all this lead the economy and the country? What are the repercussions and outcome of all this? What will happen to the several million of small and medium retail outlets functioning throughout the country, who are seeking their livelihood in the country?

The general tendency of Indians is: Those who are lucky and equipped with the needed background and resources go to schools and colleges and end up joining a job—a government one, a private one or a corporate job. A small fraction of the population do some technical courses and become professionals such as engineers, doctors, chartered accountants, lawyers, tax consultants, architects etc. What is left out to the rest of the population is either becoming unskilled workers. Some out of these small groups are a little venturesome and have the needed worldly wisdom, and they tend to start a business of

their own. Some, of course come from business communities and they may anyway end up starting their own new businesses or continue to run their family businesses.

THE CRUX OF THE STUDY

The crux of the present study is to examine whether the fears of the petty traders agitating against establishment of big corporate business houses are misplaced. If there is going to be a shift in the consumer shopping habits and they take to supermarkets thereby leaving the convenience stores and Kirana shops high and dry. Therefore it is a matter to be pondered over in depth. Instead, the entry of corporate houses into retailing is going to prove that the retailer wheeling hypothesis is to be true once again, the damage it is going to cause to the petty trader is temporary and there is nothing much to worry. In third scenario, the shift of the consumers from the convenience stores to big corporate houses is going to be on more permanent basis and the corporate houses will be able to maintain their edge over small stores. But in the long-run, it is going to cause damage to the small trader. In the fourth scenario, if the big corporate houses are able to buy truce with the respective governments by fair or foul means, it will definitely damage the livelihood of the small business men, while the national economy as a whole may benefit in the long run.

The theme of this study is to validate that that the opening of supermarkets in India is not likely to affect the lives of several millions of small and independent retailers in a big way. We further hypothesize that the segments that patronize independent retail outlets are not the same segments which patronize supermarkets. If there is an overlap between these two segments, it is marginal and not so big which will give a blow to the small retailers. We wish to caution those who are mistaking shopping malls with supermarkets. Except for the difference in the location, shops in the malls are all owner managed independents like any other street corner retail outlet .As the topic is related to the changing Indian retail scene, the study has the responsibility to project towards the end of it, the changes that are most likely to take place in future. Alternatively, it may conclude that not much is going to change in retail space in India, till several other conditions of the country and the economy change significantly . For this sort of a prognosis, we need to go through the past with regards to the historical perspective of the retailing in general and the retailing scene of India in particular. Hence, the study intends to review the history of retailing in America first, followed by the shifts that took place in the Indian retailing scene. The review will include a few studies and their conclusions for retailing in India and elsewhere.

The study envisages three kinds of shoppers: predominantly convenience stores shoppers, supermarket shoppers and shoppers who visit and buy goods in both supermarkets and convenience stores interchangeably. Also we had suggested some tentative strategic postures each type of retail outlets are supposed to adopt for each type of shopper segments. Lastly, the governments, as a part of their vote bank politics may play tricks on the public. But they cannot change the will of the public and dictate terms to the corporate houses. A case in point is; the Union government wanted the bedi (cheap cigarettes)-makers to print a picture of human skull and bones on the bedi packets. Under pressure from tobacco lobby and political parties, the state governments withdrew the order in some states.

Objectives

The specific objectives of the study are to find:

1. What do the consumers expect from a retail store?
2. To what extent the present small retail stores are offering to that of consumers expectations;
3. Are the supermarkets and big retail outlets (often located centrally) willing to offer what the consumers expect;

4. What are the characteristics of a small store shopper and a Super-market shopper from a consumer view point?

5. What should be done by the small retailer to attract and hold on to their customers?

6. Are the super-market shoppers and the small store shoppers totally different with different expectations; (if so be the case, nobody needs to worry about the other shops coming up or existing? It will be a situation of peaceful co-existence).

HYPOTHESIS

In accordance with the problem and purpose of the study, the following hypotheses were tested in this study.

H1: The market segments of convenience stores and supermarkets are independent of each other.

H2: Whatever switching taking place in the shoppers from convenience stores to supermarkets is a temporary phenomenon and is not likely to last longer.

H3: It is not difficult for the convenience stores to retain their customers, if they change their track to suit the convenience of their loyal customers.

Suggestions to the retail outlets

1. The retail outlets should do everything in the book to retain the old customers and enhance the favorable attitude of the indifferent consumers. Most of the respondents—both general store consumers and supermarket consumers allocated high score for width and depth of the product range, quality of the products and store lay out. The general stores should do whatever possible to them to improve upon their current performance. One more aspect that is binding retail store buyers to their current shops is credit facility. The general stores may develop ties with banks and financial institutions to provide this facility at least to trustworthy customers.

2. The retail store owners must indulge in personal talk with their customers to find out why they are coming to their shops. Then, they have to strengthen their performance on that count and try to retain their customer base

3. The retail store owners must find out the choice of their customers and keep all those assortments suitable for their segments. They do not have to go in for a wide range of products and deeper product lines, wasting their resources such as shelf space and money.

4. Majority of the customers in the general store segment happen to be quality conscious and price conscious, the retail store owners have to take extra precautions with regard to quality and price and they have to sharpen their procurement skills.

5. As the customers are older with lot of exposure to the real world, they are price and quality conscious. To this extent, the retail store owner will have a tough time, satisfying his customers and he has to work overtime to build store loyalty among the customers offering them several discounts etc.

5. To suit the requirement of their customers, the general stores must see to it that the pack sizes and more frequent sales to the same families. This requires invariably more helping hands. Patience on the part of retail store staff is an essential characteristic that makes the store a success

6. The assortment of the retail stores has to be chosen carefully, so that the customer can have knowledge of such products and buy them. Products such as paper napkins, toilet tissues etc. have no place in a general store going by the level of literacy and education among the customers of these stores

7. The marketer has to understand clearly as to what type of products that will fit into his store and into the families of his customers. Shops will succeed by keeping in their stores more and more time-tested products and brands rather than new and innovative entrants into the market.

8. Retailers who do not entertain bargaining are big losers in Indian markets. We find haggling and even quarreling over prices right from Kashmir to KanyaKumari, across the length and breadth of the country. In fact, our foot-path business which often runs into several lakhs of rupees in turn-over, flourishes and thrives on this count. Mark-ups may be very much high; consumers enjoy getting even a one rupee off as discount as it satisfies their ego.

9. Marketers should learn how to maintain store loyalty and enhance it among their customers. After trying all the strategies in the book, the big corporate houses learnt the hard way that their success lies in keeping themselves close to the customers. Instances are abound in which some of the big corporate houses were brought to their knees by the retailing associations, in West Bengal, Kerala, Maharashtra and several other states.

10. The retail store owner must have lot of patience. He gets more number of shoppers to his shop and many times one single customer in a week if not in a day. All these trips may not get him more business than one trip of one customer at a supermarket. But the retailers by and large have to know that this is a passing phase and most critical phase for them. They will not lose their business to the supermarkets, provided they are able to retain their customers during these trying times.

CONCLUSION

First of all, advent of supermarkets is a passing phase. The corporate houses, having learnt the hard way that the markets are ruled by retailers, wished to enter the retailing business. It could also be because it is certain that business would make profits and grow. Also it gives them opportunity to spread risk. To capture the markets quicker they are using all the gimmicks of the trade and also their large financial clout thereby luring the customers. Once they establish themselves in the market and reach a comfortable position vis-à-vis the small retailers, they are bound to follow the retailer way in terms of quality of products, prices and so on.

Secondly, the retailers do not have to go panicky, nor should the state governments vie with one another to ban of entry of corporate houses into retailing business, knowing very well that they cannot sustain that for long. The corporate houses are seemingly behaving and appear to be obeying the governments because they know that the governments cannot sustain it for long. The retailers' wheeling hypothesis will definitely set in sooner than later and the market stabilizes with each one getting his due share.

Thirdly, it is not the state governments, nor the corporate houses; it is the customer who dictates terms to the markets. Ultimately what prevails is what he wants. In a free market like ours, it is competition between small retailer as an institution and corporate retailer as an institution. 'Survival of the fittest' will rule the market at last.

Fourthly, our study proved that, there are two separate segments for this problem—one retail store consumers and the second, supermarket consumers. Though there is a little overlap between these two like in any other situation, each institution will have its share once the market shares stabilize. This is akin to a situation in which star hotels and small restaurants co-exist peacefully once the share stabilizes.

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